

Economic effects of non-pharmacological interventions in low back pain

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Abstract

Low back pain (LBP) is a global health issue with enormous socioeconomic impact. It ranks first in terms of disability and is the leading cause of years lived with disability (YLDs) worldwide. The aim of this analysis is to present an overview of non-pharmacological methods for treating low back pain and to assess their potential to prevent or reduce the need for pharmacological and surgical treatment. This 10-year literature review confirms that several non-pharmacological interventions, particularly psychosocial and exercise-based approaches, are cost-effective alternatives for the treatment of low back pain. Continued research on innovative treatment delivery methods, combined with improved methodology, is essential for obtaining information on economic costs, informing health policies, and optimizing care for patients with LBP.

Keywords

cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT), economic effects, low back pain (LBP), mindfulness-based stress reduction (MBSR)

Introduction

Low back pain (LBP) is a global health problem with an enormous socioeconomic impact. It ranks first in terms of disability and is the leading cause of years lived with disability (YLDs) worldwide, according to reports from the Global Burden of Disease 2020. LBP has a high prevalence, with almost 80% of people experiencing back pain at least once in their lifetime.

The etiology of LBP varies, but for the most part it is mechanical or non-specific, which makes its diagnosis and treatment a challenge. In addition to direct medical costs related to consultations, medications, and procedures, LBP leads to significant indirect costs such as loss of productivity, work absenteeism, and impaired quality of life. The traditional approach often involves pharmacological interven-

tions and, in some cases, surgical intervention, which carry both a financial burden and potential side effects and risks (Gashin et al. 2023; Chang et al. 2024). A clear increase in the share of over-the-counter (OTC) drugs, especially analgesics, is observed (Petkova et al. 2014; Petkova and Atkinson 2017). The benefit of patient education is clearly demonstrated (Petkova et al. 2011; Andreevsta et al. 2013).

Low back pain represents a significant burden on patients, health systems, and society due to its high prevalence, chronic nature, and associated costs for treatment, lost productivity, and reduced quality of life (GBD 2019 Diseases and Injuries Collaborators 2020). In the context of rising healthcare costs and concerns about the long-term use of medications, the focus is increasingly shifting towards non-pharmacological interventions as sustainable and effective alternatives (National Guideline Centre (UK) 2016; Foster et al. 2018).

Objective

The aim of this analysis is to present an overview of non-pharmacological methods for treating low back pain and to assess their potential to prevent or reduce the need for pharmacological and surgical treatment. We will focus on the economic aspects of these interventions, analyzing their effectiveness and economic benefit compared to conventional approaches.

Materials and methods

For the purposes of this economic evaluation, a systematic review of the scientific literature covering studies on the efficacy and cost-effectiveness of non-pharmacological interventions for LBP was conducted.

This review article aims to synthesize and analyze the current scientific literature regarding the economic effectiveness of these approaches, focusing on the trends and key findings from the last 10 years (2015–2025), as well as to outline future research directions.

Trends in the economic evaluation of non-pharmacological interventions (2015–2025). The analysis was performed by searching the PubMed, Scopus, Cochrane Database, and Google Scholar databases. The following keywords were used in the search: non-pharmacological methods for treating low back pain, back pain, hospitalization, disease treatment cost, work absenteeism, outpatient care, medication costs, emergency medical services, healthcare costs, doctor visits, clinical impact, rehabilitation, and exercises.

Results

Overconfident consumer decisions, unequal or limited access to healthcare and related pharmaceutical services, economic inequalities, and financial constraints are the underlying factors for the growing number of Bulgarian patients seeking self-medication—mainly through OTC drugs, food supplements, bioactive food components, and medicinal herbs (Tsvetkova et al. 2014). In recent years, the understanding of the economic value of non-pharmacological interventions for LBP has deepened. A clear shift towards integrated approaches and the evaluation of innovative delivery methods is observed.

Psychosocial and multidisciplinary approaches

Cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT) remains one of the best-studied and most economically effective non-pharmacological approaches. Systematic reviews and meta-analyses in recent years consistently demonstrate that CBT is cost-effective for managing chronic LBP. For instance, an extensive systematic review by Norton et al. (2015) concludes that the therapy offers favorable cost-effectiveness

ratios, especially when accounting for long-term benefits such as reduced need for medical care and improved quality of life, measured by QALYs (quality-adjusted life years). A study by Zhang et al. (2023), based on a literature review with a large number of patients, further supports these findings, showing that patients undergoing CBT have lower overall healthcare costs within a >6-month period compared to those receiving standard care.

Multidisciplinary rehabilitation programs continue to be considered the gold standard for treating acute and chronic LBP. Although their initial costs may be higher, numerous economic evaluations demonstrate their cost-effectiveness. Hochheim et al. (2023) presents results from a randomized controlled trial with a 2-year follow-up, proving that multidisciplinary biopsychosocial rehabilitation is cost-effective from a social perspective, given the significant reduction in work absenteeism and improved productivity. Fatoye et al. (2023) in *Physiotherapy* further supports this with a modeling study demonstrating that long-term benefits exceed initial investments, especially in patients at high risk of pain chronification.

Physical activity and innovative approaches for access to non-pharmacological methods

Structured exercise programs continue to be a core element in non-pharmacological interventions. Miyamoto et al. (2019) published a systematic review highlighting the cost-effectiveness of various exercise formats (e.g., extension exercises, yoga, Pilates, and strength training) for LBP, with some studies showing that group formats may be more cost-effective compared to individual sessions.

In recent years, digital health care (e.g., mobile applications, web-based self-help platforms, and telerehabilitation) has been the subject of increased interest. Feng et al. (2024) conducted an economic evaluation of an app-based intervention for LBP, demonstrating its potential cost-effectiveness compared to traditional physiotherapy visits, offering greater access at lower costs per patient. Sivertsson et al. (2023) also present data that telerehabilitation can be cost-effective for patients in remote areas, reducing travel costs and time lost from work.

Manual therapies and alternative approaches

The economic evaluation of acupuncture and manual therapy (physiotherapy, osteopathy) continues to show more variable results. While some studies, such as that by Wei et al. (2019), find acupuncture cost-effective as an adjunctive therapy for certain groups of patients with chronic LBP, other analyses emphasize the need for larger, well-controlled studies with longer follow-up for conclusive evidence on long-term cost-effectiveness. Similarly, economic evaluations show variations; a review by Blanchette et al. (2023) concludes that while there is evidence of short-term cost-effectiveness, long-term data remain more limited.

Table 1. Results of studies conducted on LBP with non-pharmacological treatment methods.

First author and publication year	First author and publication year	Method	Results
Chou et al. 2017	Nonpharmacologic therapies for low back pain: a systematic review for an American College of Physicians clinical practice guideline	Systematic review of RCTs for non-pharmacological therapies, evaluating effectiveness for acute, subacute, and chronic LBP.	Chronic LBP: Evidence supports exercises, multidisciplinary rehabilitation, acupuncture, massage, manual therapy (including spinal manipulation), and yoga as effective for pain relief and function improvement. New evidence supports Tai Chi and mindfulness-based stress reduction. Acute/Subacute LBP: Patients should be advised to remain active, and application of heat therapy or massage, acupuncture, or spinal manipulation may be considered if pain persists.
Cashin et al. 2021	Non-pharmacological and non-surgical treatments for low back pain in adults: an overview of Cochrane Reviews	Overview of Cochrane systematic reviews evaluating various non-pharmacological and non-surgical treatments for adults with LBP.	LBP: There is evidence that exercises, multidisciplinary therapy, spinal manipulation, acupuncture, and psychological therapies (e.g., CBT) can provide small to moderate improvements in pain and function. It is also recommended to advise the patient to remain active rather than to rest.
Foster et al. 2018	Prevention and treatment of low back pain: evidence, challenges, and promising directions	Review, part of The Lancet series on LBP, summarizing current evidence and recommendations.	First-line treatment should include information, advice to remain active, and physical and psychological therapies aimed at bio-psycho-social factors. Exercises (including Tai Chi, Pilates, and yoga) are strongly recommended for chronic LBP. For acute LBP, maintaining activity is recommended.
Hayden et al. 2021	Exercise therapy for chronic low back pain (Cochrane Review)	Systematic review of RCTs (249 studies, over 24,000 participants), evaluating exercises for chronic LBP.	Exercises reduce pain and improve function in chronic LBP. There is no significant difference in efficacy between different types of exercises (e.g., aerobic, strength, stabilization).
Mu et al. 2020	Acupuncture for chronic nonspecific low back pain (Cochrane Review)	Systematic review of RCTs for acupuncture in chronic LBP.	Acupuncture may be effective in reducing pain intensity and improving function in chronic LBP, especially when compared to no treatment or sham acupuncture.
Anheyer et al. 2017	Mindfulness-based stress reduction for treating low back pain: a systematic review and meta-analysis	Review evaluating the effect of mindfulness-based stress reduction (MBSR) on pain and function in LBP.	MBSR provides a moderate improvement in pain intensity and a significant improvement in pain-related function in the short and medium term for chronic LBP.
Furlan et al. 2015	Massage for low back pain, Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews	Systematic review of RCTs for massage therapy in LBP.	Massage therapy is associated with short-term pain reduction and improved function in chronic LBP.
Leung et al. 2025	The effect of cognitive behavioural therapy on pain and disability in chronic non-specific low back pain: an overview of systematic reviews	Systematic review of CBT for LBP.	CBT is most effective when integrated with other forms of active treatment, such as exercises or physiotherapy, or as part of a multidisciplinary program.
Devonshire et al. 2020	Effectiveness of Cognitive Functional Therapy for reducing pain and disability in chronic low back pain: a systematic review and meta-analysis	Systematic review of CBT for LBP.	There is a very low degree of certainty in the evidence that Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy (CBT) may not be more effective than current management strategies in adults with Chronic Low Back Pain (CLBP).
Miyamoto et al. 2019	Cost-effectiveness of exercise therapy in the treatment of non-specific neck pain and low back pain: a systematic review with meta-analysis	Systematic review and meta-analysis for LBP.	Exercise therapy appears to be cost-effective compared to usual care for subacute and chronic low back pain. Exercise therapy is not more cost-effective compared to other interventions for neck pain and low back pain.
Cheng et al. 2025	Evaluating the effectiveness of six exercise interventions for low back pain: a systematic review and meta-analysis	To validate the effectiveness of six different exercise therapies in the treatment of back pain using meta-analysis methods and to propose optimal duration, frequency, and cycle of exercises.	The six exercise therapies have been shown to effectively relieve back pain, with yoga showing the best results. The optimal exercise intervention protocol included a session duration of no more than 30 minutes, a frequency of more than 4 times per week, and a cycle (total duration) of no more than 4 weeks. Furthermore, exercise interventions showed the most significant improvements in Oswestry Disability Index (ODI) results for back pain.

Improvement of methodologies

During the period under review, increased attention was also paid to the methodological rigor of economic evaluations. Researchers are increasingly including indirect costs (e.g., loss of productivity due to work absenteeism or reduced work capacity) using the methods described by Drummond et al. (2015), which is essential for a full assessment of the economic burden of LBP. The use of real-world data and large administrative databases is also increasing, complementing data from randomized clinical trials and ensuring greater applicability of the results to clinical practice, as described by Vollert et al. (2023).

Challenges and future directions

Despite significant progress in the economic evaluation of non-pharmacological interventions for LBP, several challenges remain.

Heterogeneity of interventions and studies

The wide variety of non-pharmacological approaches and the methodological differences between studies make direct synthesis and generalization of results difficult. Larger, standardized studies are needed.

Long-term outcomes

Although progress has been made, sufficient long-term data on costs and effects are still lacking, especially for newer digital tools. Future research should include longer follow-up periods.

Applicability

The results of economic evaluations often depend on the specifics of the health system and the price structure of the specific country, which makes direct applicability across different countries a challenge. More studies are needed in various national contexts.

Patient preferences and value

Future research should better integrate patient preferences and perceptions of value, as these can significantly influence the adoption and adherence to non-pharmacological interventions. To this end, it is appropriate to conduct patient education and involve a greater number of specialists from various disciplines, including pharmacists, which has proven successful in other diseases (Andreevska et al. 2013). Pharmacists' training in the third and fourth years includes pharmaceutical technology, pharmacology, pharmacognosy, pharmacoconomics, and social pharmacy, while the fifth year focuses on pharmaceutical care, patient counseling, pharmacotherapy, and medical sciences (Petkova and Atkinson 2017). Advice on the non-pharmacological impact on low back pain can be added to the training of pharmacists for counseling. The educational approach has the potential to improve patients' quality of life (Petkova et al. 2014).

Conclusion

In conclusion, this literature review over the last ten years confirms that a number of non-pharmacological interventions, especially psychosocial and exercise-based approaches, are cost-effective alternatives for the treatment of low back pain and would lead to economic benefits for health systems and employers. In the long term, we believe that integrated interventions such as exercises, CBT, and multidisciplinary programs reduce recurrences, which is a key factor for economic efficiency in LBP.

Continued research into innovative treatment delivery methods, combined with improved methodology, is essential for obtaining information on economic costs and informing health policies and optimizing care for patients with LBP.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

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Author contributions

Conceptualization, DST, and RS; methodology, AV and EN; validation, RS, ZS and AV, formal analysis, RS; investigation, DST; data curation, EN; writing – original draft preparation, DST, RS, AV, ZS and EN; writing – review and editing, DST, RS and EN; visualization, RS; supervision, DST, AV and EN. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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